

Newsletter

August 2023

**BUILD
SMARTER.
CLEANER.
CHEAPER.**

Dear changemaker,

BIMprove project is coming to an end and this will be the last Newsletter. We are impressed about how much new has actually been created in the project and want to celebrate our results with you.

Among other things, we have developed:

- 🛠️ An interface where you can set up paths / routes for data capture by drone or robot, directly in the BIM.
- ✅ Effective linking of progress plan and BIM provides better insight and follow-up of progress.
- 🎯 Sensors on the construction site and image recognition that reveal safety challenges make the follow-up of construction projects data-driven and safer.
- 🔧 And when everything is put into context, the way we carry out construction projects is revolutionised.

BIMprove celebrates its Final Review meeting in Lausanne, Switzerland

On 15th June, BIMprove consortium reunited in Lausanne in order to showcase to the European Commission the final results of three years of hard work aiming at improving Building Information Modelling (BIM) by real time tracing of construction processes.

Watch the summary video!

Have we succeeded? Let's find out!

Do you want to discover our progress?

WP 1 – System design and specification

The main goal of WP1 – Systems design & specification is to specify the concept, design and KPIs for whole BIMprove system, which other WPs were relying on. WP was defining BIMprove's overall system design, which includes Digital Twin model, layer services and all workflows. Also, all of Pilot Use Cases (Fire, Safety and Scheduling) were more detailed defined.

WP 2 – Components, technologies and functionalities

In the last project period, the main work in WP2 consisted in elaborating and establishing the communication between the individual satellites. In addition, systems were improved on the basis of initial experience at construction sites.

and piloting

This Workpackage has been about bringing everything together – integrating the different parts and functionalities and testing them on the pilot construction sites.

WP 4 – Impact, Outreach and Collaboration

In the picture on the left you can see the main highlights from our Impact and outreach strategies. When it comes to exploitation and standardization important outcomes have been achieved. Keep reading to learn more!

[Read the full article to learn more!](#)

Do not miss our Impact Miniseries!

BIMprove has worked hard to bring our project's great results forward and get the attention from the general public that it deserves. Therefore, a few months ago we designed the "Impact Miniseries" campaign to bring the project to a close, through interviews to key project partners. This campaign highlights the lessons learnt in the project, the ground-breaking tech BIMprove has developed and the social impact that these will create.

[Visit our website](#) to watch all interviews!

Check the most outstanding BIMprove results

In this article, we provide an overview of what has been developed in the frame of BIMprove from the perspective of the final users, our industrial partners. Most functions of the BIMprove system have reached a prototype stage by M24 (as planned) and testing of the overall system has been started on the three Pilot Use-Case locations.

BIMprove contribution to standardisation

A working committee with members of the BIMprove team together with external experts has prepared a CEN/CENELEC workshop agreement: **“Position markers for digital applications on construction sites, structural monitoring and BIM-applications”**.

This workshop agreement CWA standardises markers to be used by modern digital applications: devices like (laser-) scanners, autonomous vehicles, augmented reality devices and others, that are increasingly used by the construction industry.

The final version will be presented to the public for consultation and comment and its final version published in autumn 2023.

[Learn more about this in our brand-new website page!](#)

Markers

Position markers for digital applications on construction sites, structural monitoring and BIM-applications

**Thanks for joining forces,
Thanks for being part of the change!**

We are leading the European construction industry to a low-carbon, climate-resilient digital transformation, do you want to keep contributing to this mission?

Do not miss the ongoing European projects revolutionising the construction industry!

SEE YOU AROUND!

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